

Management Strategies that Affecting Teaching Quality Management and Students' Learning Outcome in Higher Vocational Colleges

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Abstract: This paper aims to examine management strategies that influence online course learning outcomes in the context of digital education, and the links between educational resources and teacher management and student learning outcomes. High quality talents come from the high efficiency teaching management and sufficient educational resources of the school, and high quality talents depend on the school educational resources to a large extent. Educational resources in higher vocational colleges are one of the important factors that affect students' learning outcomes. A variety of management strategies from different perspectives have an impact on teaching quality, and then affect students' learning outcomes, which requires university administrators to plan and allocate educational resources. Through public interviews with five experts from "double high" demonstration higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province, China, two conclusions are drawn: First, it can be concluded that university leaders mainly manage learning outcomes through educational resources, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement. Then, attempts are made to highlight the significant relationship between educational resources and student learning outcomes. This study will help university leaders and principals realize the importance of teaching quality management and identify the factors that improve the quality of school education and thus affect student learning outcomes.

Keywords: teaching quality management, student learning outcomes, educational resources, teacher professional development, curriculum management, continuous quality improvement.

Introduction

In modern Education, especially in Higher Vocational Education (HVE), management strategies and educational resources play a crucial role in improving student learning outcomes. Higher vocational colleges shoulder the heavy responsibility of training technical

talents. Facing the changing social needs and technological progress, how to effectively manage educational resources and improve students' learning results has become the focus of education administrators' attention. This paper aims to explore which management strategies have a significant impact on online course learning outcomes in the context of digital education, and how educational resource management affects student learning outcomes.

Research background

With the rapid development of economic globalization and science and technology, the demand for high-quality technical talents is growing day by day. As an important base for training such talents, the importance of higher vocational education has become increasingly prominent. However, higher vocational education also faces many challenges in the development process, such as uneven allocation of teaching resources, uneven quality of education, and difficult to meet the individual needs of students.

According to the report "China's Education Modernization 2035" released by the Ministry of Education, the number of higher vocational colleges has reached 1,486, with more than 15.9 million students, accounting for nearly half of the total scale of higher education. This huge education system has a huge demand for educational resources, and how to efficiently manage and allocate these resources has become the key to the development of higher vocational education.

Under the background of digital education, education and teaching are facing great changes. The rapid development of digital technology has brought earth-shaking changes to the field of education, especially the rise of online education, which provides new opportunities for the education resource management and teaching mode of higher vocational colleges. Digital teaching resources, such as network courses and virtual laboratories, not only enrich the teaching content, but also improve the flexibility and accessibility of teaching. Online education is spreading rapidly around the world, and digital education has become an important part of teaching in higher vocational colleges. In this context, how to improve students' learning outcomes through effective management strategies has become the focus of education administrators and researchers. Educational resources in higher vocational colleges are important factors that affect students' learning results. Reasonable management of educational resources can significantly improve students' learning results.

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the global online education market has grown exponentially over the past decade and is expected to reach \$325 billion by 2025 (UNESCO, 2020). In China, the Action Plan for Improving the Quality of Vocational Education (2020-2023) issued by the Ministry of Education clearly points out that vocational colleges should vigorously develop online education and improve the level of education informatization (Ministry of Education, 2020). Under this background, higher vocational colleges are facing new challenges and opportunities in the management of educational resources and teaching strategies.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this paper is to verify the management strategies that affect online course learning outcomes in the context of digital education, and to explore the links between educational resource management and student learning outcomes. Through public interviews with 5 experts from higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province, this paper aims to draw the following two conclusions: First, university leaders manage learning outcomes mainly through educational resources, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement; Secondly, it tries to highlight the significant relationship between educational resources and student learning outcomes.

Problem Statement

Although there has been a great deal of research on the impact of educational resources and management strategies on student learning outcomes, there is still limited research in the specific field of education of higher vocational colleges, especially in the context of China. Through field research and expert interviews with higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province, this paper will deeply explore the relationship between educational resource management and student learning outcomes, as well as the role of different management strategies in this process.

Research significance

This study will help administrators and educators in higher vocational colleges to understand how to improve teaching quality through effective management strategies, so as to improve students' learning outcomes. The research results will provide theoretical support and practical guidance for the management of educational resources and teaching strategies in higher vocational colleges.

Literature review

Educational resources and student learning outcomes

Educational resources include hardware facilities, software resources, teaching materials, etc., which directly affect students' learning environment and learning effect. Research shows that sufficient educational resources can stimulate students' interest in learning, improve learning efficiency, and thus enhance students' learning outcomes. Factors such as the diversity of educational resources, teaching quality, learning environment, practical ability cultivation, learning outcome evaluation system and equitable distribution of educational resources jointly affect students' learning outcomes (Grissmer, 2013). The diversity of educational resources means that students can acquire a wider range of knowledge, skills and experiences, which can include textbooks, teaching equipment, online resources, practical activities, etc. The diversity of educational resources can meet the different needs of students, stimulate their learning interests, and thus improve their learning outcomes (Rahman et al.,2010). Teaching quality is one of the key factors of learning outcomes. Excellent teachers, reasonable teaching methods and perfect teaching process play an important role in improving students' learning depth. Teachers should have solid professional knowledge, good teaching ability and rich teaching experience, and be able to adjust teaching strategies according to the actual situation of students, help students deeply understand knowledge and improve learning results (Dai, 2021).

Teacher professional development and student learning outcomes

Teachers are the core elements in the process of education, and their professional quality and teaching ability directly affect the quality of teaching. By providing continuous professional development opportunities, teachers can improve their teaching standards, which in turn improves student learning outcomes. The professional growth of teachers not only improves their personal teaching skills and knowledge, but also has a direct impact on improving the quality of education and students' academic performance (Powell & Bodur, 2016). Educational research shows that teachers are the key factors affecting students' learning outcomes, and teacher professional development activities, such as training and continuous learning, can significantly improve teachers' teaching quality and directly enhance students' learning results (Dahri et al.,2021). Teachers themselves are also learners, and through professional development, teachers are constantly learning new teaching methods and strategies, which helps them better understand the needs of students and develop more effective teaching plans, thus improving students' academic performance (Dorgu, 2015).

Curriculum management and student learning outcomes

Curriculum management includes curriculum design, curriculum implementation and curriculum evaluation, which is an important factor affecting teaching quality. Scientific and reasonable curriculum management can ensure that the teaching content is scientific and systematic, improve the teaching effect, and thus enhance the learning results of students. Good curriculum management can ensure the effective allocation of educational resources and improve the quality of teaching, thus directly affecting the learning outcomes of students (Ayeni & Akinfolari, 2014). Curriculum management requires clear teaching objectives, which should be closely linked to student learning outcomes. Through reverse design principles, course content and teaching strategies are designed based on expected learning outcomes (Dimmock, 2013). Curriculum management should ensure that teaching content is in harmony with teaching strategies to support students in achieving learning objectives, which includes the selection of appropriate teaching methods and assessment methods to promote in-depth learning and understanding (Ayeni & Akinfolari, 2014). Effective curriculum management involves continuous evaluation and improvement of the teaching process, which means adjusting teaching methods and course content based on student feedback and learning outcomes (Glasman et al., 2002). Curriculum management also involves the provision of necessary learning support and resources such as library services, tutoring and technical support, which are important factors for students to achieve good learning outcomes (EA., 2020). Curriculum management should include assessment and feedback on student learning outcomes, which helps students understand their progress and areas for improvement (Chance & Peck, 2015). The quality of curriculum management directly affects the effectiveness of education and students' learning outcomes. By ensuring coherence and consistency in curriculum design, implementation, and evaluation, students' academic performance and overall educational experience can be improved (Sabrina et al., 2022).

Continuous quality improvement and student learning outcomes

Continuous quality improvement is a systematic and continuous management strategy to improve teaching quality and student learning outcomes through continuous feedback and improvement. Continuous quality improvement requires school administrators and teachers to constantly reflect and improve the teaching process to ensure the continuous improvement of teaching quality. Continuous quality improvement (CQI) process emphasizes the achievement of curriculum goals to drive the improvement of teaching quality. Through the observation and measurement of learning outcomes, educators can judge the achievement of curriculum goals and make teaching improvement based on it (Harper & Lattuca, 2010). Continuous quality improvement requires teachers to analyze and diagnose their own teaching behavior and find out the existing deficiencies, so as to provide a basis for continuous improvement of teaching quality (Bernhardt, 2017). CQI usually adopts the PDCA (plan-do-check-act) cycle to achieve continuous improvement in teaching quality. This cycle involves making improvement plans, executing them, checking the effects, and making adjustments based on feedback (Zhong et al., 2023). In the CQI process, educational evaluation and feedback is the key link. Through evaluation and feedback, educators can understand the situation of educational process and outcomes, adjust teaching strategies and methods in time, and improve the quality of education (Clark, 1993).

Research Methodology

The research object is to conduct in-depth interviews with 5 teaching management experts from five higher vocational colleges under the "double high" construction in Guangdong Province (Shenzhen Vocational and Technical University, Shenzhen Information Vocational and Technical College, Guangdong Light Industry Vocational and Technical College, Guangzhou Panyu Vocational and Technical College, Shunde Polytechnic).

Through semi-structured interviews, experts' views and experiences on educational resources, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement were collected. The interview covers the following aspects: the management and distribution of educational resources, the importance of teacher professional development and implementation strategies, effective methods and experiences of curriculum management, and the application and effect of continuous quality improvement in teaching.

All the experts are core leaders of the school management, with more than 20 years of work experience, and serve as associate professors in China. Expert information makes the interview results more convincing and reliable. The purpose of the expert interview is to discover the unknown, i.e. a person's "inside knowledge", and the expert interview helps to conduct a good interview quickly and easily. This method is widely accepted by experts. This study adopts a qualitative approach to explore the impact of management strategies on students' learning outcomes.

Table 1: Interview question development

No.	Questions	Source
1	How to effectively construct and manage professional teaching resources to meet the needs of students and teachers?	Yue (2012)
2	How to effectively allocate laboratories, equipment and other practical resources to support the implementation of the curriculum and the development of students' practical ability?	Li (2020)
3	How to establish an internal quality assurance system that ADAPTS to the characteristics of higher vocational colleges in order to continuously improve the teaching quality?	Liu (2016)
4	How to build an effective digital quality diagnosis platform to help schools monitor and improve teaching quality in real time?	Zhuo (2019)
5	How do school administrators manage teacher qualifications to Improve Teacher Quality?	Gabrielle (2019); Wulandari (2020); Ahmad, Shaheen & Hussain, 2022)
6	How does the school administrator's management of teacher quality improve your personal improvement?	Wenglinsky, (2000); Marzano & Waters (2009); Goe, (2007).
7	What strategies will your college use to improve teacher quality?	Pharis, Wu, Sullivan & Moore (2019); Cochran-Smith, (2021).
8	what are the In-service Training Strategies to Improve Teacher Quality?	Tuncel & Çobanoğlu, (2018). GÜN, (2021)
9	What are the Classroom Management Strategies to Improve Teacher Quality?	Franklin & Harrington, (2019); Francis & Oluwatovin (2019).

Research Finding

Management and distribution of educational resources

The interview results show that the management of educational resources in higher vocational colleges is an important factor affecting students' learning outcomes. Experts agree that adequate educational resources can provide students with a good learning environment and

improve learning results. Specifically, the reasonable allocation and management of educational resources, including the improvement of hardware facilities and the update of teaching software, teacher professional development. (Expert 1) emphasizes that teacher professional development plays an important role in improving teaching quality and students' learning outcomes. By providing professional training and further education opportunities, teachers can continuously improve their teaching ability and professional quality, so as to improve the teaching effect. Expert 2 suggested that vocational colleges should strengthen support and training for teachers and provide more opportunities for professional development. (Expert 3) believes that sufficient educational resources can provide students with a good learning environment and promote their learning motivation and effect. Especially in the context of digital education, rich digital teaching resources and perfect network learning platform are crucial to improve students' online learning results.

Teacher's professional development

Teacher professional development is an important means to improve teaching quality. Experts pointed out that through regular teacher training and further education, teachers' professionalism and teaching ability can be improved, so as to better cope with the challenges of online education. The support of teacher professional development not only helps to improve the teaching level of individual teachers, but also promotes the overall progress of the teaching team. The teaching supervision and curriculum management of higher vocational colleges are related to the performance of teachers in the classroom. The quality of teachers is controlled through the check of new teachers, the encouragement of education promotion and the qualification of teachers. In addition, "set up a teaching steering committee, set up a supervision office, innovate management concepts, and carry out teaching competitions". (Expert 1); Funds have been set up to encourage teachers to further their education through various training, teaching skills competitions, disciplinary inspections, and open teaching. (Expert 2) Expert; Qualification certificate attachment, temporary exercise and performance management are important measures. (Expert 3) can conclude that there are other strategies related to teacher quality, competition in teaching skills, research ability, and teaching resources. But the main strategies adopted by administrators are curriculum management, teacher qualifications and on-the-job training.

Curriculum management

In terms of curriculum management, experts believe that scientific and reasonable curriculum design and implementation are of great significance to the improvement of students' learning outcomes. Through systematic curriculum design, we can ensure that the teaching content is scientific and systematic, which can improve the learning effect of students. In addition, curriculum evaluation is also an important part of curriculum management. Through the evaluation of curriculum effects, curriculum content and teaching methods can be continuously improved to enhance teaching quality. (Expert 1) believes that teachers strictly implement teaching management rules and regulations to ensure that students come to the classroom on time and have normal classroom teaching; (Expert 2) Emphasize on strengthening teachers' teaching skills, improving the maintenance and updating of teaching equipment, and promoting modern teaching equipment in classroom teaching; Teaching supervision system, teaching supervision and guidance. Pay attention to teaching evaluation and teaching skills purposefully and pertinently. (Panelist 3) In my school, installing cameras in classrooms and using the Internet for administrative supervision and classroom inspections are the most popular. Experts believe that reasonable course design and teaching content arrangement can effectively enhance students' learning interest and learning effect. In the context of digital education, course management also needs to take into account the characteristics of online teaching, such as curriculum flexibility, interaction and so on.

Continuous Quality Improvement

Experts agree that continuous quality improvement is an effective management strategy that continuously improves teaching quality and student learning outcomes. Experts stressed that higher vocational colleges should establish a sound quality feedback mechanism to encourage teachers and students to participate in the evaluation and improvement of teaching quality. Through regular teaching evaluation and feedback, problems existing in the teaching process can be found, and timely adjustment and improvement can be made, so as to continuously improve the teaching quality and students' learning outcomes.

Student learning outcomes

Impact on students' Learning outcomes According to the experts' views on the topic "What impact does the improvement of teachers' professional development have on students' learning outcomes?" Expert feedback is as follows. "In my class, students interact more with me, have higher exam pass rates, fewer make-up exams, better after-school literacy and greater motivation to learn." (Expert 1) The promotion rate of education has been improved, and the classroom atmosphere, classroom discipline and spirit are better than before; (Expert 2) Fully feel students' enthusiasm and initiative in learning, students' strong desire to interact with me, and create a good classroom atmosphere; (Expert 3) Students have a high degree of concentration in class and a good level of professional skills, and we are often praised by internship organizations. Student learning outcomes are mainly related to student performance in the course, including online test results, mutual comments with teachers, high pass rates and good assignment completion.

Discussion

Through the expert interview analysis of management strategies that affect teaching quality, we find three main themes: education management strategies, teacher professional development management strategies, curriculum management strategies and continuous quality improvement management strategies. In addition, the relationship between educational management strategies, teacher professional development management strategies, curriculum management strategies and continuous quality improvement management strategies on teaching quality and student learning outcomes can be obtained. These conclusions are consistent with the literature review above and provide a validation and qualitative empirical test of the relationship between educational resource management and student learning outcomes studied in this study.

The affection of teaching management strategies on students' learning outcomes

Through the analysis of the interview data, it can be seen that educational resource management, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement are important factors affecting students' learning outcomes. Reasonable management of educational resources can provide students with a good learning environment and improve the learning effect. Teacher professional development can improve teaching quality and students' learning outcomes. Scientific curriculum management can ensure that the teaching content is systematic and scientific, and improve the learning effect of students. Continuous quality improvement can continuously improve the quality of teaching and thus improve the learning outcomes of students. Zhang et al. (2020) believes that online teaching infrastructure, teacher experience and information gap have significant impacts on online teaching effects, and government policy support and educational resources have positive effects on promoting online teaching. Ummat & Retnowati (2022) found that social capital has a positive impact on students' learning outcomes. The better students' social interaction and family support in the learning environment, the higher the learning effect. Intrinsic motivation has also been proved to have a positive and significant impact on students' learning outcomes.

Wynter et al. (2019) found that despite the trend of e-learning, traditional resources, such as attending face-to-face lectures, are still an important factor affecting students' learning effect. Lin et al. (2017) showed that digital learning has a better positive impact on learning effect than traditional teaching, and learning motivation has a significant positive impact on learning effect. Learning motivation has a significant positive impact on learning benefits in learning outcomes. Researchers believe that combining the current teaching trend, making use of the advantages of digital learning and formulating feasible teaching strategies are conducive to improving teaching effects. The results show that there is a significant relationship between educational resources and student learning outcomes. Sufficient educational resources can provide students with good learning conditions, stimulate learning interest, enhance learning efficiency, and thus improve learning outcomes. The rational management and distribution of educational resources is the key to improve students' learning outcomes.

The affection of teacher professional development management strategies on student learning outcomes

Ally (2019) believes that teachers' digital ability can make a significant contribution to education and promote students' learning and education development. Through teacher training, digital ability can be improved, professional knowledge can be acquired, and students' learning outcomes can be improved. Gonzalez-Perez & Ramirez-Montoya (2022) analyzed which components of Education 4.0 were considered in the 21st Century Skills framework and identified affected teaching methods and key stakeholders. The researchers conducted a systematic literature review of the research questions. It is revealed that teachers and schools lack these frameworks, and most of them are student-oriented, and develop abilities through the dimensions of personality, meta-learning and associative active learning teaching strategies to promote the improvement of students' learning effects. Pak et al. (2020) Scholars agree that teacher professional development is a key mechanism to implement educational policies that require teachers to change, and professional development usually needs to be content-centered, active, collaborative, coherent and continuous, and the application of this framework has a positive impact on student learning results. The results show that there is a significant relationship between teacher professional development and student learning outcomes. The results show that the learning effect of students in e-learning is determined by the teaching ability of educators, and the teaching ability of educators plays a crucial role in determining students' learning outcomes.

The affection of curriculum management strategies on students' learning outcomes

Premalatha (2019) believes that the evaluation of curriculum outcomes is the most prominent aspect to improve the quality of education. The credits of each course are based on project outcomes and project-specific outcomes, and it is necessary to improve the evaluation of learning outcomes through the curriculum design of teachers. Amon & Bustami (2021) discussed curriculum management and the implementation of school-based management in school-based learning, and the results showed that to improve the implementation and effectiveness of school-based management, it is necessary to improve the ability of principals, teachers and school committees to implement school-based management. Improving the staff's ability to make operational and teaching changes can effectively carry out the course management and learning process, shape the character of students, improve academic performance, and improve the quality of education. Ni 'mah et al.(2024) observed the direct implementation of results-based education through a blended learning platform, emphasizing student interaction and teaching effects, and found that the implementation of learning management system has been proven to effectively improve student learning outcomes. The results show that there is a significant relationship between curriculum management and student learning outcomes. Good curriculum management can ensure the effective allocation of educational resources, improve the quality of teaching, and directly affect the learning

outcomes of students.

The affection of continuous quality improvement management strategies on student learning outcomes

King & Herrmann (2015) researchers believe that by comprehensively evaluating its learning outcomes, a project can identify shortcomings, improve curriculum and other activities, and students' learning quality management and process improvement are conducive to improving students' learning outcomes. Namoun et al. (2019) provides a comprehensive self-assessment tool for identifying strengths and weaknesses at all stages of the continuous quality improvement cycle and evaluating the learning outcomes of various undergraduate education programs. Quality experts can use the managed CQI self-assessment tool to determine the relationship between their continuous quality improvement cycle and the learning outcomes of various disciplines. Takriff et al. (2011) reported on the process of obtaining student feedback, how the information was handled, and the improvement measures implemented. Student feedback was obtained through online course evaluation systems, student dialogues, and graduation surveys of graduating classes. We believe that results-based engineering education (OBE) requires continuous quality improvement (CQI) to ensure that students achieve the expected learning outcomes. The results show that there is a significant relationship between continuous quality improvement and student learning outcomes. Continuous quality improvement is a dynamic, circular process that promotes the improvement of student learning outcomes through continuous evaluation and improvement of teaching practices, an approach that not only contributes to the improvement of current student learning outcomes.

Conclusion & Suggestion

Conclusion

Through interviews with experts from higher vocational colleges in Guangdong Province, this study verifies the impact of educational resource management, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement on student learning outcomes. The results show that these management strategies play an important role in improving students' learning outcomes. There is a significant relationship between educational resources and students' learning outcomes. Reasonable management of educational resources can significantly improve students' learning results. The aim of the research is to provide valuable information and guidance for researchers, scholars, policy makers and stakeholders as well as teachers to effectively manage teaching quality and produce competitive graduates. This paper discusses the research of school teaching quality management from the aspects of education resource management, teacher professional development, curriculum management, continuous quality improvement and student learning outcomes, which is of great significance for understanding how to improve teachers' professional quality and train high quality graduates. The effects of educational resource management, teacher professional development, curriculum management and continuous quality improvement on teaching quality management and student learning outcomes were systematically reviewed. It has been suggested that school personnel management should consider teacher qualifications when recruiting teachers. Make arrangements to improve the management of teachers' qualifications so as to produce effective teaching methods and the quality level of students. School leaders should strive to improve the quality of teachers, enhance their professionalism and teaching performance; In-service strategies and mentoring strategies have positive effects on teachers' work performance. It is suggested that schools should provide relevant policies to support teachers to participate in teacher professional competence training in the teaching profession.

Suggestion

Based on the research results, the following recommendations are made:

1. Strengthen the management and distribution of educational resources to ensure that students have sufficient learning resources.
2. Provide more professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their teaching ability and professional quality.
3. Adopt scientific and reasonable curriculum management methods to ensure systematic and scientific teaching content.
4. Establish a sound continuous quality improvement mechanism to continuously improve teaching quality and student learning outcomes.

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